

ANALYSIS CHAIN TO DETERMINE THE CHEMICAL REACTION PATH BETWEEN CARBON FIBER SURFACE, SIZING AND RESIN

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ABSTRACT

In commercial production carbon fibers are coated with a sizing immediately after the electrochemical activation. On the one hand the sizing protects the fibers from damage during textile processing; on the other hand it controls the formation of the interface between resin and fiber in carbon fiber reinforced polymers. For an optimized fiber matrix adhesion the chemistry of the fiber surface, the sizing and the resin need to be adjusted to each other. To this end knowledge of the chemical reactions at the fiber matrix interface is needed. Here we present an investigation to identify the possible chemical reaction paths between the carbon fiber surface, the functional groups of the sizing and the resin system. At first, the unsized carbon fiber and the pure sizing are analyzed to serve as a reference for the impact of the following treatment steps. In order to investigate the dependence of the interaction of fiber and sizing on the degree of fiber activation, two different activations of carbon fibers were performed before a sizing was applied. Two different types of sizing were used: a sizing, possessing only one epoxy group per molecule and a more reactive sizing, possessing several epoxy groups per molecule. In order to further analyze the covalently bonded sizing layer fibers are subjected to hot solvent extraction. Then the extracted fiber is exposed to an epoxy equivalent weight titration to determine the remaining reactivity of the covalently bonded layer. The detected epoxy groups are available to bond to the resin, allowing a better stress transfer from the resin to the fiber and thus improving the mechanical properties of the composite. This work emphasizes the importance of a chemical understanding of fiber surface, sizing, resin matrix and the interfaces between them.

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of applications for carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) in industry is growing rapidly. The performance of the CFRP depends on the kind of fiber and matrix used and, in particular, on the fiber matrix interface formed during production. Strong interfacial interactions, such as the formation of covalent bonds, are assumed to improve mechanical properties [1]. After carbonization, the surface of industrial carbon fibers is usually activated by electrochemical oxidation and then impregnated with a sizing. The sizing is needed to protect the fibers from damage during textile processing, but should also support the formation of an interface to function as a strong joint between carbon fiber and resin. As a consequence the three components, fiber, sizing, and polymeric matrix, need to be tuned chemically to each other. Therefore, a study of the interfacial reactions between them is considered to be important for a better understanding of the properties of the final composite product.

The wet electrochemical activation is applied to the fibers to generate a hydrophilic surface that is equipped with functional groups ready to react with the sizing and/or the resin. The advantages provided by the electrochemical activation over other activation processes is the small space necessary and the few by-products released [2-6]. The electrochemical activation yields various hydrophilic

functional groups on the carbon fiber surface, i.e. nitrogen groups as amines and pyridines and oxygen containing functional groups as alcohols, carbonyls or carboxyls, as displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Possible functional groups created on the carbon fiber surface by electrochemical oxidation.

In the following we will focus on the interaction between the fiber surface and epoxy based sizings. Then these species can be categorized according to their ability to react with the epoxy groups of the sizing. Epoxides react with nucleophiles, as alcohols and amines, under cleavage of the three-membered carbon ring [7-8]. However, the standard reactions for nucleophilic opening of epoxides are often far from ideal and usually encounter some obstacles such as need for high acidity [9], basicity and/or high temperature [10]. The reaction rates are assumed to increase in the order carbonyl < alcohols < phenols < amines ~ carboxyl.

Carbonyls do not show any reactivity towards the epoxy functionalities of the sizing under the typical conditions of the sizing process [18]. The phenols exhibit the highest reactivity of the various alcohols. Still a temperature significantly above room temperature is needed to catalyze the reaction; the reaction scheme is depicted in Figure 2. Since the aqueous sizing polymer solution has a slightly acidic character the reaction temperature might be decreased compared to a reaction under neutral conditions [10]. For various epoxy sizings the reaction with the phenolic groups of the carbon fiber surface is assumed to take place around 150-160 °C [11,18].

Figure 2: Reaction scheme of an alcoholic group with the epoxy functionality of a polymer.

Additionally, amines are found on the carbon fiber surface. The reaction scheme of an amine with an epoxy group is shown in Figure 3. Comparative studies [12-15] of the reactivity of primary and secondary amines assign higher reactivity of the primary amines. The ratio of the reaction rate constant of the secondary amine addition to that of the primary amine addition depends on the electron donating properties of the amine and may vary with the temperature [16-17].

Figure 3: Reaction scheme of a primary amine with an epoxy functionality of a polymer.

Carboxylic functional groups show the highest potential for a fast reaction with the epoxy groups of the sizing. The reaction scheme is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Reactions scheme of carboxylic group with an epoxy functionality.

Since the formation of oxygen containing groups on the carbon fiber surface can be controlled in wet electrochemical oxidation, in the following we focus on the effect of varying concentrations of these groups. Former studies showed that the interlaminar shear strength and the interfacial shear strength of CFRP materials increase with the amount of oxygen groups on the carbon fiber surface [1,19-23]. Similar findings are expected for the fiber-sizing interaction. Some publications have already addressed this topic [20]. In this work we will elucidate the correlation between the interaction between the carbon fiber surface and the sizing and the degree of fiber activation.

The surface resulting from the reaction between carbon fiber functional groups and the sizing, also needs to bond to the resin. This could happen via chemical or physical interactions. Due to the higher bonding strength, chemical bonding is expected to result in better adhesive properties. The probability of the formation of chemical bonds to the matrix resin should increase with the number of reactive groups of the sizing. Only one of the sizings investigated (Epoxy 2), possesses several reactive epoxy groups and is expected to form covalent bonds with the carbon fiber and the resin. The other investigated sizing (Epoxy 1) possesses only one epoxy group per molecule and, therefore, should either form bonds to the carbon fiber or the resin.

To analyze the amount of reactive epoxy groups on the sized carbon fiber surface, the part of the sizing which did not chemically react with the carbon fiber surface has to be removed, to expose the covalently bonded sizing layer. Hot solvent extraction is used for this purpose.

In order to determine the remaining reactivity of the extracted fiber, the fiber is exposed to an epoxy equivalent weight (EEW)-titration. The detected epoxy groups indicate the reactivity of the sizing layer to react with the hardener of the resin system and form the desired bond between the fiber and the resin. The analysis revealed a remaining reactivity of the fibers sized with Epoxy 2 and showed no remaining reactivity for fibers with Epoxy 1 sizing, as expected. In this paper we will show that the use of sizing with several reactive end groups promotes a covalent bonding between sized carbon fiber and epoxy resin and should be advantageous for adhesion between fiber and resin.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Surface treatment of the carbon fibers

Untreated 50k polyacrylnitril-based carbon fibers were supplied by the production line of SGL ACF in Moses Lake. The electrochemical activation and the sizing application to the untreated carbon fibers were performed in a dynamic process on a pilot line. The fibers were activated by a charge density of 10 C/g. After activation the fibers were sized with two epoxy based sizings differing in the amount of reactive epoxy groups per molecule and molecule size. Epoxy 1 holds only one epoxy group per molecule, Epoxy 2 in contrast has several epoxy groups per molecule. The characteristic parameters of the sizings are summarized in Table 1. After sizing application the fibers were dried at a temperature of 160°C. The sizing process is controlled in order to gain 1 wt% of dried sizing on the final fiber surface.

System	Molecule Size [nm]	EEW [Eq/g]
Epoxy 1	32	56
Epoxy 2	153	3,713

Table 1: Molecule size and number of epoxy equivalents per gram measured by EEW-titration of the polymeric epoxy sizings Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2.

2.2 Surface analysis

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) spectra were recorded with a Physical Electronics Versa Probe II using an Al $K\alpha_{1,2}$ x-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) in the monochromatic mode at 24.6 W at a pressure below $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Pascal. All data were collected and stored with 128 channel mode detection. The spectrometer was operated with a spot size of 100 μm and a Pass Energy of 23.5 eV resulting in an energy resolution of 0.1 eV. Data processing such as peak area calculation and shifting was performed via MultiPak Version 9.5.0.8 © Ulvac-phi, Inc.

Chemical composition is determined by analysis of the XPS peak areas, corrected by the element and orbital specific sensitivity factors. The functionality of the surface atoms is investigated by fitting the C1s spectra with a suitable number of lines. The energy position of these lines defines the respective chemical shifts and allows identification of the type of bonded functional groups. The spectra are fitted with pseudo Voigt lines with the parameters of peak area, full width at half maximum and peak position. For the C1s peak five separate lines are fitted. The ratio of the respective functional groups is determined by the peak areas. For each type of fiber at least 5 spectra were recorded at different positions on the prepared fiber bundle.

For detailed analysis of the nanostructure of the separated fibrils, AFM measurements of uncoated fibrils were carried out using a Bruker Dimension ICON atomic force microscope in tapping mode with TESPA AFM probes from Bruker with a tip diameter of 8 nm. The scan size of the images was 5 μm , scanned with a rate of 0.5 Hz and 1024 samples/line. The lateral resolution was about 10 nm, while the noise of the z-piezo was 35 pm. Analysis of the images was performed using Matlab R2010a with an algorithm developed by Ref. [Jäger], to determine the fibril and nano roughness of the surface. At least three AFM images were recorded per fiber type. Average roughness values are calculated from more than three individual values.

Hot extraction was carried out by a Soxhlet apparatus from BÜCHI. The fibers were introduced into a glass filter and extracted in Soxhlet equipment in a continuous flow of 80 ml of methyl ethyl ketone for 3 h.

EEW titration was performed to determine the epoxy equivalent weight (EEW) of the sizing, and was performed following ASTM D 1652.[24] The polymer was dissolved in 10–15 ml of methylene chloride, and 10 ml of a tetraethyl ammonium bromide solution was then added to the mixture. The sample was titrated with a 0.1 molar perchloric acid/peracetic acid solution in pure acetic acid until the indicator, crystal violet, changed colour from blue to green. The EEW-titration was performed on three samples per fiber type.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Carbon fiber activation

Important for the interaction between carbon fiber, sizing and resin are the functional groups on the carbon fiber surface as well as the topography of the carbon fiber surface [25-30]. The relevant surface for our investigation is that of the activated carbon fiber. Therefore, the carbonized, untreated carbon fiber is activated by wet electrochemical activation to two different degrees, resulting in two different degrees of oxidation as well as two configurations of functional groups on the carbon fiber surface. The untreated carbon fiber serves as a reference.

Chemical analysis of the carbon fiber surfaces by XPS reveals only carbon, oxygen and nitrogen. The chemical composition of the fibers is summarized in Table 2. The untreated carbon fiber is characterized by 96.9 at% carbon, 1.2 at% nitrogen and 1.8 at% oxygen. The medium treated fiber shows significantly higher concentrations of nitrogen and oxygen of 1.6 at% and 7.8 at%, respectively. For the highly treated fiber a further increase of nitrogen and oxygen is observed (2.1 at% and 12.1 at%).

System	C [at%]	N [at%]	O [at%]
Untreated Carbon Fiber	96.9 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.6
Medium treated Carbon Fiber	90.6 ± 0.5	1.6 ± 0.4	7.8 ± 0.5
Highly treated Carbon Fiber	85.2 ± 2.0	2.1 ± 1.0	12.2 ± 1.2

Table 2: Chemical composition of carbon fiber surfaces.

Figure 1 a to 1c show the XPS C1s peaks of the un-, medium- and highly-treated carbon fibers. To compare the C 1s spectra of the differently activated carbon fibers they are overlaid and depicted in figure 1d. The difference in the peak appearance at the high binding energy side of the C1s peak is especially pronounced between the highly activated carbon fiber and the two other ones. Although there is a significant difference in the oxygen and nitrogen concentration between the untreated and medium treated fiber, this is not reflected in the corresponding carbon 1s peak.

For a more in-depth analysis of the functionalization of the carbon fiber surfaces the C1s peaks are fitted following the procedures described above. All carbon fiber C1s peaks exhibit a main peak centered at 284.8 eV with a pronounced shoulder at the high binding energy side. This shoulder is resolved into four peaks, shifted from the main peak by approximately 1.4 eV, 2.3 eV, 4.1 eV and 6.3 eV. These peaks correspond to the chemical shift of alcohol/ether/epoxy groups, carbonyl groups, carboxyl/ester groups and a characteristic plasmon loss[31]. The peaks originating from the nitrogen functional groups overlap strongly with these four peaks and cannot be separated by the fitting procedure. As the nitrogen content is clearly lower than the oxygen content for all three types of fibers, the influence of nitrogen containing groups on the peak shape is neglected in the following. In Table 3 the ratios of the fitted peak areas are summarized. There is almost no change between the untreated and the medium treated fiber, while for the highly treated fiber a significant increase of carbonyl and carboxyl/ester groups is observed. The relative ratios of the different functional groups change as well. For the highly activated carbon fiber the amount of carboxylic functional groups exceeds the values of the carbonyl groups.

Figure 5: Fitted C1s XPS spectra of the carbon fiber surface a) untreated, b) medium activated and c) highly activated carbon fiber, d) overlay of the C1s spectra of the untreated, medium and highly activated carbon fiber.

System	C-OR [%]	C=O [%]	COOR [%]	C _{sat.} [%]
Untreated Carbon Fiber	16.02 ± 0.9	3.9 ± 0.2	3.6 ± 0.2	5.8 ± 0.3
Medium treated Carbon Fiber	17.26 ± 1.5	4.3 ± 0.3	3.1 ± 0.5	4.8 ± 0.6
Highly treated Carbon Fiber	16.24 ± 1.7	4.8 ± 0.6	5.2 ± 1.0	1.9 ± 1.0

Table 3: Peak area of various functional groups normalized to integrated intensity of the C1s spectrum.

The fibers were also investigated by AFM with respect to their surface roughness. The topography of the untreated carbon fibers and the activated carbon fibers are compared. Concerning the fiber topography, structures of different scales have to be addressed, namely fibril and nano structures on top of the fibrils. The fibril diameter is about 100 nm, while nano structures have a size around 10 nm. As determined by Ref. [34] the mean roughness R_a of these nano structures for sized carbon fibers shows an overall value of around 0.1 nm while unsized carbon fibers have a nano roughness of around 0.4 nm. Total background corrected height analysis shows an even distribution of these nano structures on top of the fibrils of the unsized fibers, whereas for the sized fibers the nano structures are not present [34]. The background corrected height analysis of our fibers, the untreated fiber and the highly activated fiber, is shown in Figure 6. An overlay of AFM height images (gray scale) and nano roughness (colour scale) is done, as introduced by Ref. [34], to visualize the lateral distribution of the nano structures on the fiber surface. For all three types of fibers a high density of nano structures is detected, homogeneously distributed over the surface. In Table 4 the fibril and nano roughness of the fibers is summarized. Within the margins of error all fibers – the untreated fiber, the medium activated fiber and the highly activated fiber – show the same fibril and nano roughness. The activation treatment thus does not change the roughness of the fibers, neither on fibril nor on nano scale. These results are in agreement with previous investigations of Ref. [40].

Figure 6: AFM images of the a) untreated and b) treated carbon fiber surface. Overlay of height image (gray) and nano roughness (colour scale).

System	Fibril roughness [nm]	Nano roughness [nm]
Untreated	15 ± 3.0	0.6 ± 0.10
Medium treated	17 ± 5.0	0.7 ± 0.17
Highly treated	21 ± 5.0	0.7 ± 0.15

Table 4: Fibril and nano roughness of the carbon fibers.

4.2 Sized carbon fibers

In order to identify the influence of the functionalization and of the reactivity of the sizing on the reaction path, the three types of fibers were coated with the two sizings.

Figure 7 displays the XPS C1s spectra of the sized carbon fibers with sizing Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2. Since the amount of sizing results in a layer thickness of about 50-100 nm, while the escape depth of the electrons detected by XPS does not exceed 10 nm[35], only the sizing layer is analyzed by XPS. Chemical analysis of the sized fiber surface reveals the elements carbon and oxygen. Both sized fibers (Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2) show the same chemical composition with about 80 at% carbon and about 20 at% oxygen, as summarized in Table 5. The C1s peak is characterized by a clear double structure, as displayed in Figure 7a. It is fitted with two lines at binding energies of 284.8 eV and 286.2 eV (see Figure 7b), corresponding to the main structure and the alcohol/ether/epoxy groups of the sizing. The average ratio of the two structures, summarized in Table 5, does not depend on the type of sizing. The XPS data of the two sizings are nearly identical, even though the two sizings exhibit completely different EEW values. This can be explained by the similar main polymeric structure of the two epoxy based sizings.

Figure 7: C1s XPS spectra of the carbon fiber surface (a) sized with Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2 and (b) fitted XPS C1s spectrum of the sized carbon fiber.

Sized Carbon Fiber	C [at%]	O [at%]	C-C [%]	C-OR [%]
Epoxy 1	80.2 ± 2.7	19.8 ± 2.5	61.9 ± 3.2	38.15 ± 3.2
Epoxy 2	79.7 ± 3.2	20.3 ± 2.9	60.9 ± 4.4	39.15 ± 3.7

Table 5: Chemical composition of the carbon fiber surface and peak area of various functional groups normalized to integrated intensity of the C1s spectrum.

In Figure 8 the AFM images of both sized fibers are shown. Again, the height image (gray scale) is overlaid with the nano structures (colour scale). The sized fibers exhibit a significant decrease of the density of the nano scale features compared to the unsized fibers. Comparing the two different sizings, Epoxy 1 results in a slightly higher density of nano structures than Epoxy 2.

In Table 5 the fibril and nano roughness values of the sized fibers are summarized. A significantly reduced fibril and nano roughness compared to the unsized fibers is found. No differences in fibril roughness are observed for the two types of sized fibers, whereas sizing Epoxy 1 shows a slightly higher nano roughness than Epoxy 2.

Figure 8: AFM images of the carbon fiber surfaces sized with sizing a) Epoxy 1 and b) Epoxy 2. Overlay of height image (gray) and nano roughness (colour scale).

System	Fibril roughness [nm]	Nano roughness [nm]
Sized Fiber Epoxy 1	7 ± 4.0	0.2 ± 0.12
Sized Fiber Epoxy 2	6 ± 3.0	0.1 ± 0.09

Table 6: Fibril and nano roughness of the sized carbon fibers.

4.3 Extracted carbon fiber exposing the covalently bonded sizing layer

The sized carbon fibers were extracted, so that only the covalently bonded polymeric sizing molecules remain on the carbon fiber surface, while the physically bonded molecules are removed. Analyzing the extracted carbon fiber via EEW titration allows the determination of the remaining epoxy reactivity of the fiber surface. These remaining epoxy groups are considered to be the most important ones to form covalent bonds with the amine based hardener of the resin.

The surface of both extracted fibers, extracted from sizing Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2, is analyzed by AFM. The resulting roughness values are summarized in Table 7 and the AFM images (overlay of height and nano roughness) are depicted in Figure 9. The images resemble those of the unsized fibers. A high density of nano structures is observed on both fiber types. Also the resulting fibril and nano roughness values of the extracted fibers are independent on the former sizing type and similar to the values of the unsized carbon fibers. The results indicate that the molecules physically bonded to the fiber were largely washed off by the extraction method.

Figure 9: AFM pictures of the carbon fiber surfaces extracted from sizing a) Epoxy 1 and b) Epoxy 2. Overlay of height image (gray) and nano roughness (colour scale).

System	Fibril roughness [nm]	Nano roughness [nm]
Extracted Fiber Epoxy 1	18.0 ± 4.8	0.70 ± 0.20
Extracted Fiber Epoxy 2	15.8 ± 1.3	0.53 ± 0.42

Table 7: Fibril and nano roughness of the carbon fibers after solvent extraction.

By XPS the chemical reaction between fiber and sizing and the correlation to the type of sizing and the degree of activation of the carbon fiber surface can be further investigated using the resulting oxygen groups as a fingerprint. The C1s peaks of both extracted fibers are shown in Figure 10a. The appearance of a shoulder at energies around 286.2 eV can be correlated to the remaining amount of sizing on the carbon fiber surface. It is assigned to the alcohol/ester/epoxy groups. Epoxy 1 has a smaller shoulder than Epoxy 2 for the same activation of the carbon fiber surface. This can be explained by the higher amount of epoxy groups of sizing Epoxy 2 or the higher molecular size of the sizing. In Figure 10b, exemplary for Epoxy 1, the XPS C1s spectra of the differently activated and extracted fibers are depicted. The magnitude of the shoulder is correlated to the degree of activation of the carbon fiber surface. This result indicates a higher interaction between the carbon fiber surface and the sizing for a higher amount of functional groups on the fiber surface. The activation process thus is decisive for the interaction between carbon fiber and sizing and represents an important tool for optimization of fiber sizing adhesion.

Figure 10: C1s XPS spectra of the carbon fiber surface after Soxhlet extraction a) from Epoxy 1 and Epoxy 2 and b) of untreated, medium and highly activated carbon fibers sized and extracted with Epoxy 1.

4.4 Remaining reactivity of the sized fiber towards the resin

After exposure of the covalently bonded sizing layer on the carbon fiber, the reactivity of these remaining sizings molecules is investigated. To this end, extracted carbon fibers are subjected to an EEW-Titration, in order to determine the remaining epoxy reactivity. The corresponding values can be found in Table 8. As expected, for Epoxy 1 no reactive epoxy groups are detected. The single epoxy group of this sizing has bonded to the fiber surface and, correspondingly, no further epoxy groups are available. Even though higher amounts of sizing Epoxy 1 were found on the exposed carbon fiber surface for highly activated carbon fibers (see Figure 10b), these fibers show no detectable epoxy groups. Therefore, the larger shoulder observed for the higher activated carbon fiber is attributed to a higher amount of bonded sizing molecules with oxygen functionalities other than epoxy, e.g. alcohol or ether.

For Epoxy 2 a EEW value of 2.7 Eq/g is measured on the extracted fiber surface. This value confirms the existence of epoxy groups for sizing Epoxy 2, which may easily react with the primary amines of the hardener. The use of epoxy sizings with a higher number of epoxy groups thus seems to

be promising for increased chemical reaction with the resin and optimized adhesion properties of fiber and resin.

System	EEW [Eq/g]
Epoxy 1	0,0
Epoxy 2	2,7

Table 8: Epoxy equivalents per gram measured via EEW-Titration of the extracted fibers.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this work an analysis chain is presented to investigate the reaction path between carbon fiber surface, epoxy based sizing and epoxy resin.

First, the influence of electrochemical activation of the carbon fiber surface on the fiber-sizing interaction was investigated. The fiber sizing interaction can be tuned by the carbon fiber activation process. A higher degree of surface activation results in a higher amount of sizing molecules bonded covalently to the fiber surface.

Secondly, the remaining epoxy reactivity of sizing molecules covalently bonded to the fiber surface was analyzed. The epoxy reactivity was determined by desizing of the fibers and subsequent EEW titration. Two different types of sizing were used, differing in their amount of reactive epoxy groups per molecules. For sizing Epoxy 1, which has one epoxy group per molecule, no remaining epoxy groups were detected after extraction. The single epoxy group has bonded to the fiber surface, no further groups are available. For sizing Epoxy 2, holding several epoxy groups per molecule, the EEW value of the extracted fibers confirmed the existence of a considerable amount of epoxy groups. Additional to the covalent bonding of the sizing molecule to the fiber surface, further active epoxy groups remain. Several epoxy groups per sizing molecule thus provide the possibility of covalent bonding to both components - the carbon fiber surface and the epoxy resin system.

Both described aspects are important for covalent bonding between fiber, sizing and resin, which is assumed to be advantageous for improved fiber matrix adhesion and enhanced mechanical properties of the resulting composite material. The analysis chain allows detailed investigation of the fiber-sizing-resin interaction and allows specific optimization of the process steps.

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